

Relationship Between Interpersonal Trust And Positive Mood Among Educational Counselors

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History Received: Mach 04, 2020 Accepted: June 14, 2020	<i>The aim of the research was to identify the Relationship between Interpersonal Trust and Positive Mood Among Educational Counselors. The researcher used the descriptive method and the sample of the study reached (150) educational counselors. The researcher used two Scales: the Interpersonal Trust scale and the Positive Mood scale. The validity of both instruments was verified validity (face, and construction, Translation) and consistency of the instruments using the re-test, and internal consistency Cronbach's alpha. Interpersonal Trust among Educational Counselors was (91.4067) this refers to a higher level, compared with the theoretical average of (75). Positive Mood among Educational Counselors was (36.4800) this refers to a higher level, compared with the theoretical average of (30) ,The research found that there is no significant correlation between the Interpersonal Trust and Positive Mood of the educational counselors.</i>
Keywords Interpersonal Trust, Positive Mood, and educational counselors	
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1. Introduction

The interpersonal trust generally affects relationships between community members, employees, and groups in organizations. Widespread distrust leads to the disintegration of the social structure (Rotter, 1980, p. 1). A mutual interpersonal trust leads to the greatest possible success when it is involved in social relationships with others. It also helps to avoid many negative aspects that occur in the nature of social relationships (Ibrahim, 2014: 26).

Through the researcher's field experience during her interviews with a number of educational counselors over the years. It was found to her that there is a weakness in the mutual Interpersonal Trust between many educational counselors in their relations with the teaching bodies and school administrations, which in turn leads to difficulty in communication and social interaction among them, which affects the psychological and social aspects as well as aspects of their personalities.

Positive Mood (Positive Mood) makes the educational counselor consciously seek to preserve his positive feelings and make him more able to help others maintain their positive mood, especially when help is helpful (Carlson, Charlin, & Miller, 1988, p. 212).

A number of researchers have emphasized in their studies that positive mood has an important influence on the performance of the individual's tasks and improvement, setting goals clearly for him, innovation in solving problems, activating cognitive treatments for problems and decision-making (Hom and Arbuckle, 1988, p.114)).

Consequently, the research problem addresses the identification of the interpersonal trust and its relationship with Positive Mood among educational counselors, because no previous study was conducted - according to the researcher's knowledge - to examine these two variables among educational counselors.

Research importance:

The extension work is one of the most important services provided to help the guides achieve the maximum level of personal and social harmony that will reflect positively on the achievement. The goals of the extension work are energy investment and manpower development. Naturally, this specialized and humanitarian work is qualified in terms of efficiency and practice (Al-Shehri, 2000: 9).

The psychological counseling focused on modifying the guides' attitudes or their attitudes towards their problems because it leads them to change or modify their behavior in a positive way because human behavior is flexible and adjustable. This feature gives counselors an opportunity to deal positively to identify the problem and determine the causes and how to address it (Al-Azza, 2001, 27).

The psychological counselor plays a prominent role in achieving the goals of counseling, building the personality of the guide and integrating it, and helping him to face his problems that hinder his healthy psychological growth by developing his potentials, so the psychological counselor must assume his various responsibilities, roles and functions related to the guiding positions (Al-Jumaili and Al-Bajari, 2008: 309)

Interpersonal trust is vital in daily human interaction, as it affects the individual's interaction with others in both good and bad interactions, as well as with friends and hostility (Gurin & Gurin, 1970, p.84). In the study of McAllister (1995), its results revealed that the availability of an interpersonal trust affects the enhancement of interactive and cooperative behavior and the strengthening and strengthening of coordinated actions. It also found that trust encourages working in the spirit of a specialized work team, without any prior knowledge or influence on others. (McAllister, 1995 , p. 26).

Positive Mood can be caused by its occurrence in humans by its interaction with many different aspects of life, and also as a result of the effects of others, Positive Mood is usually a state that occurs without there being a clear reason for identifying it. Many individuals cannot determine exactly why they are in a positive mood, and it seems that individuals are in a positive mood when they have a restful day and a good night's sleep, and they do not feel stress in their lives, and many studies conducted on the effect of Positive Mood on the cognitive processes of Human, it has shown that Positive Mood can affect our minds in good ways in general, and it has been found that Positive Mood enhances problem-solving and flexibility in thinking, and some studies have reported that Positive Mood allows individuals to work freely and be more creative, as it helps individuals in situations where thinking requires In complex operations, it requires brainstorming, increased selection of information and more attention to it, thus making it easier for them to complete the tasks with less effort and a shorter time by increasing access to relevant information that contributes to the success of problem solving, thus improving their performance at work (Rowe & Anderson, 2007, p. 383).

The educational counselor has an important and influential role that requires him to have a positive mood, and he is especially important for performing tasks and reinforcing them. It leads to more positive memories in his interactions with co-workers and with mentors, consequently, adopting more positive behaviors to help others (George, 1989, p. 318).

Positive Mood makes the educational counselor aware of his positive emotions and consciously seeks to preserve them, and is more able to help the counselors and maintain their positive mood (Carlson, Charlin, & Miller, 1988, p. 212).

Bell (1978) asserted that an individual's Positive Mood attracts Positive Mood more easily to co-workers by influencing their moods on them, which increases the frequency of assistance provided to them and increases interactions between them (Bell, 1978, p.616).

The researcher believes that Positive Mood for the educational counselor enables him to play his role successfully in the counseling process and help the guides in identifying their problems and training them to solve them and understand themselves so that they can achieve mental health.

Research aims:

The current research aims to identify:

- Interpersonal Trust for Educational Advisors.
- Positive Mood with educational counselors.
- The relationship between the Interpersonal Trust and Positive Mood for educational counselors.

Search limits:

The current research is limited to educational counselors working in intermediate, middle and secondary schools affiliated with the Ministry of Education in Baghdad Governorate for the academic year (2017-2018).

Defining terms:

1- Interpersonal Trust:

Gurin & Gurin, (1970) defined it as: the expectation of the general impulse and the main motive that causes the occurrence of the behavior, and it depends on the fees and sizes of a certain class of things and the value of the motivation, which includes the goal or the subject. And it depends on expecting or guessing the probability that this behavior will lead to the desired goal, it depends on expectations, restrictions imposed and objective rewards that are subject to temporary changes, and also as a result of past situations.

Rotter (1980) defined it as the expectation of an individual's generalization of a promise, word, verbal or written word, or statement from another person or group .

Williams, (2014) defined it as an individual has a perception of others that they will not do anything that would harm him, and the individual shows a willingness to accept weakness or risk based on expectations about another person's behavior .

The researcher adopted Rotter's (1980) definition of mutual social trust as a theoretical definition of the research.

- Procedural definition: The researcher defines the interpersonal trust, by way of interpersonal trust, as the overall score obtained by the educational counselor through his response to the statements of the Interpersonal Trust scale as a tool for this research.

2- Positive Mood Positive Mood

Tellegen (1985) defined it as a good mood and a pleasant, positive engagement .

Watson et al. (1988) defined it as the individual's feeling of enthusiasm, activity, pleasure and alertness is a state of high energy, complete focus, and enjoyable sharing .

Watson (2000) describes positive emotional experiences of mood that are distinctive and influential and have an important role in information processing, problem solving and positive behavior with others.

The researcher adopted the definition of Watson (2000), a theoretical definition of positive mood for research.

Procedural definition: The researcher Procedurally Defining Positive Mood as the overall score obtained by the educational counselor (the research sample) through his response to the statements of Positive Mood scale prepared by the researcher in this research.

Theoretical framework:

First: Interpersonal Trust

Trust is a big part of relationships. Trust provides the basis on which close relationships can be built and allows relationships to function effectively and with satisfaction between the people involved. Research studies and studies have focused on confidence on differences in expectations for people to behave in honest and reliable ways (Rotter, 1967, p. 23).

An interpersonal trust represents an individual's trust in other individuals with whom he has little personal experience, despite their important influence in life. In order to determine the degree of his trust in others, the individual must generalize his experience with the other to them (Carl and Billari, 2014, p1).

Interpersonal trust has direct impacts on business and performance, and indirectly affects individual performance. The goal of building trust with others is to make other individuals work actively and effectively and to get rid of negative feelings and distrust that weaken joint performance and cooperation between them (Yeatts and Hyden, 1998, p.102).

Interpersonal trust role:

The interpersonal trust affects the work of individuals as follows:

- Motivates individuals and encourages them to innovate and modernize.
- It helps to hold together the individuals working in the institution.
- Helps to make social relationships successful.
- Others depend on positive expectations about their behavior, on which the Interpersonal Trust is based.
- The effective role of social mutual trust in managing complex social relationships (Hole and Lindsay: 1975, p. 187)

- An interpersonal trust raises efficiency to the highest level of success.

- It helps to avoid many negative aspects that mar the nature of social relationships(Ibrahim 1995, p. 26).

Interpersonal Trust Theories

1 - Erikson theory (Erikson 1963)

Erikson's theory in 1968 represented human development in eight stages: Each stage represents a type of development challenge facing individuals fraught with crises and represents a turning point in their lives. And when they succeed in solving crises, they are more successful in protecting their mental health (Santrock, 2009, p. 73). Building mutual interpersonal trust takes place in the first stage of the stages, called the stage (trust - lack of confidence). Building trust and building relationships in the first stage is based on parents or their representatives to provide care for the child and meet his needs. Relationships that are characterized by strong trust as a result of satisfying needs at this stage lays the foundation upon which most future social relations are based, and without instilling strong trust in the same individual, he will hesitate to form relationships with others. The feeling of confidence is based on the individual's ability to predict the behavior of others, so he begins his relationships closer to distrust and has a feeling that removes unpleasant emotional relationships (Solomon, 2003: 114-115)

2- Router theory (Rotter, 1967):

A reciprocal interpersonal trust is obtained by the individual from a generalized expectation of experiences related to novelty that characterizes a particular situation and its modernity, and Rutter emphasized that the expected generalizations are a fundamental factor in determining behavior and changing it and then predicting and generalizing (Rotter, 1971, p. 25).

The individual's expectations differ in degree from one situation to another, even if the situations are similar to a certain degree, and his expectation corresponds to the expectations of a specific situation he has passed through, and he is in this particular situation. And that selection is what characterizes the behavior of the individual, and the generalization of the situation to other future situations depends on the previous experiences of this situation (Rotter, 1980, p.2).

The generalized expectation is the dependence of the individual on what the other individual or society gives in terms of promise. There are also differences in the degree to which the individual feels that he can rely on what others say to him, and that he does what they say. And that these differences are called "general

expectations" by the individual, whether he trusts others or not, and general expectations have effects on the behavior of others in social situations, whether at home or at work (Nazmi, 2001: 115).

Characteristics of a mutual interpersonal trust:

Roten mentioned a number of interpersonal trust characteristics as follows:

Individuals with the Interpersonal Trust are loving others and make friends with both low and high confidence.

People with very high discipline and less cheating or stealing, and they give others a second chance.

Respect the rights of others, they enjoy psychological compatibility and have high self-confidence.

They have good intentions towards others, take good positions, and are not naive or vulnerable to exploitation from less trusted others.

Third: Rothenberg's theory (Rotenberg, 1994):

Rotenberg (1994) proposed the theory of mutual interpersonal trust by adopting three foundations for building a mutual interpersonal trust through relying on others, fulfilling a word or promise, honesty, and not causing harm to others. Truth-telling and conducting behaviors guided by the individual show good intentions and clear methods of dealing instead of deceit, procrastination and elusiveness (Rotenberg, 2010, p.9).

Components of Interpersonal Trust:

Mutual social trust has three basic components:

Trust Beliefs: It is the cognitive and emotional aspect and includes the individual's beliefs and feelings, and it entrenches and establishes other aspects of trust.

Approved behavior: It is reliable behavior that includes the behavior of the individual approved by others at work.

Behavior performance: It is trustworthy behavior whose individuals perform behaviors based on the three foundations of trust.

(Rotenberg, 2010, p. 10)

The foundations of a mutual interpersonal trust:

There are three foundations of mutual social trust that Rotenberg identified in his theory:

-Reliability: It is fulfillment of promises made by others.

-Honesty: It is telling the truth and performing behaviors that are distinguished by honesty, away from deception, procrastination and procrastination.

-Doing no harm: is relying on and trusting others to treat emotional harm and eliminate it, and to avoid doing actions that would lead to embarrassment (Rotenberg, 2010, p. 12).

Second: Positive Mood:

The mood:

Mood is the emotional state of the individual, and the mood is less specific, less intense and less likely to be provoked by a specific stimulus or event, and a mood is usually described either as positive or negative and others are described as being in a good mood or a bad mood. Mood also differs by describing it as a mood from personality traits that are longer lasting. However, personality traits such as optimism and neuroticism lead to a certain mood, and long-term disorders such as depression and bipolar disorder are mood disorders, and mood is the internal self-state. It can be inferred from the attitudes and behaviors of the individual (Schinnerer, JL 2007, p. 23).

Mood is not intentional or intentional and is characterized by having a comprehensive and wide-ranging effect on many different other variables, and it tends to be biased in judgments towards others (Clore & Parrot, 1991, p. 107), and mood is seen as two-dimensional like arousal - Calm or good - not good, and it can direct individual moods on both the direct and indirect levels (Russell & Bullock, 1986, p.97).

Positive mood:

When individuals are in a positive mood, most of their life situations go smoothly, Positive Mood affects the learning process, by increasing the pleasure in learning, increasing the remembering processes, stimulating memory and cognitive processes, creative problem-solving skills and increasing the overall level of task performance (Verleur et al., 2007, p.1012)). And that the individual evaluates the results in a more positive way when he is in a positive mood, and has an effect on his cognitive processes. More varied good and positive results have been obtained in cognitive contexts in the event that the individual is in a positive mood (Isen, 1999, p. 56)

And to achieve Positive Mood when individuals are exposed to certain incentives such as listening to music or showing a short film, or offering small rewards to individuals (Verleur et al., 2007, p. 1010). It has an effect on stimulating motivation and increasing productivity. Individuals with Positive Mood are persistent in their performance and the more positive the mood, the higher they have levels of motivation, and the results of studies and research have shown that Positive Mood affects the cognitive aspect of the processes beyond motivation (Erez, & Isen, 2002, p.1065)

Advantages of positive mood:

Studies have shown several advantages for individuals with Positive Mood, including:

-Their perception and evaluation of others is more positive. There is a relationship between Positive Mood and resilience (Forgas & Bower, 1987, p. 55).

-Positive Mood is related to emotional experiences of a cognitive nature that are more flexible. They treat things and situations in a more complete way (Isen & Shalke, 1982, p. 59).

- Several studies have shown empirical results in the effect of Positive Mood on individuals in making judgments and increasing creativity, openness and social status in them (Isen, 1987, p.205).

-They are distinguished by their sense of happiness and a sense of pleasure in movement and the sharing of their games with others (Isen & Shalke, 1982, p.60).

-Their vague facial expressions are more positive, and their level of mental alertness increases (Schiffenbauer, 1974, p. 32).

- They rate their jobs more positively by increasing their attention (Weiss et al., 1999, p. 12).

Research Methodology:

The researcher adopted the descriptive research method to achieve the goals of her research, which is not limited to collecting and classifying data, but rather goes beyond that because it includes a degree of interpretation of these data. Using it, he can make predictions about future events (Atwi, 2000: 172).

Research community: The current research community includes educational counselors in intermediate, preparatory and secondary schools for the education of Baghdad governorate, whose number is (457) educational counselors. Table (1) illustrates that.

Table (1)

The research community is distributed according to the directorates of education in Baghdad governorate

Education directorates in Baghdad governorate	Educational counselors
Al-Karkh first	40
Karkh second	84
Al-Karkh third	135
Rusafa first	64
Rusafa second	77
Rusafa third	57
Total	457

The basic research sample: The main research sample consisted of (150) educational counselors chosen by the random stratified method according to roughly proportional to their number in the research community. Table (2) shows that.

Table (2)

The main Sample of Research

Directorates of Education	Educational counselors
	13
Al-Karkh first	28
Karkh second	44
Al-Karkh third	21
Rusafa first	25
Rusafa second	19
Rusafa third	150

Research instruments:

First: The Interpersonal Trust Scale:

Interpersonal Trust Scale in its original form:

The router scale (1980) consisted of (25) statements, with a five-point scale, designed according to Likert's method, and the weights of alternatives were determined for the positive statements from (very agree = 5 to, absolutely disagree = 1), and for negative passages from (very agree = 1 to, totally disagree = 5), and the highest score that the respondent gets is (125) and the lowest score is (25), with a theoretical average of (75).

Interpersonal Trust Mutual Scale Procedures in Current Research:

Validate scale:

The validity indicators were verified (translation, outward, and constructive truthfulness) as follows:

- Translation veracity:

The researcher translated the Interpersonal Trust scale into Arabic and vice versa. The translated version was presented to two experts of English bilingual and psychological sciences to verify their views on the translation and indicate its accuracy, and to make appropriate amendments to the translated statements, then the agreement percentage in both cases reached (80%) and is valid according to Bloom's opinion if the percentage of agreement between the arbitrators is 75% or more of the scale can be trusted (Bloom, 1983: 126).

-Virtual validity:

(Ebel) indicates that the best way to verify the validity of the test is presented to a number of specialists to evaluate the extent to which the test items meet the characteristics that must be measured (Ebel, 1972, P.566). The apparent validity of the scale and its instructions were verified. The researcher presented it in a questionnaire to (10) arbitrators specialized in psychological sciences, and the researcher approved the approval of (8) arbitrators or more as a criterion for the relevance of the scale's statements for the current research, and no statement was excluded from the scale, so the scale remained consisting of (25) statements. (Ebel, 1972, p. 566).

= Validity of construction: The psychological construction theory believes that the strength of the correlation between the statements prepared to measure the trait is a statistical indicator of construct validity (Odeh, 1985: 165) and verification of the strength of distinguishing the statements, which is an indicator of the validity of the scale construction, and the consistency of the statements, which appears through the correlation. Each statement has an overall score on the scale, and they were all significant, and it indicates the validity of the construction of the interpersonal trust scale.

Statistical analysis:

Distinguishing Power of Statements:

The ability of the statements to distinguish between individuals who own the characteristic or the feature and those who do not possess it, is an indication of the validity of the construction. (Melhem, 2000: 19)

To achieve this, the scale was applied to the statistical analysis sample drawn from the research community, consisting of (200) educational counselors, and (27%) of the sample individuals were approved in determining the upper and lower groups in the total score. After applying the scale to the sample, the answers were arranged in descending order from the highest total score to the lowest overall score, then a percentage (27%) was determined for the two extremist groups of educational counselors, so the number of educational counselors became (54) educational counselors in each group, and the use of the t-test t- test for two independent samples to find out the significance of the differences between the two extreme groups in the scores of each statement of the interpersonal trust scale, so all the statements of the scale appeared distinct at the level (0.05) because the calculated T value is greater than the tabular T (1.96) with a degree of freedom (106), see Table (3).

Table (3)
Discriminatory Strength of Interpersonal Trust Scales

No	Upper Group		Lower group		T - value
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
1	4.574074	0.5356	1.12963	0.5843	31.934
2	3.648148	1.3758	1.425926	0.9029	9.924
3	4.518519	0.7707	1.240741	0.6424	24.007
4	3.592593	1.4343	1.185185	0.6464	11.245
5	3.462963	1.2087	1.574074	1.2378	8.023
6	4.537037	0.6358	1.148148	0.4078	32.968
7	4.574074	0.5356	1.222222	0.5016	33.567
8	4.462963	0.7451	1.259259	0.5887	24.791
9	4.574074	0.6325	1.018519	0.1361	40.384
10	4.592593	0.5327	1.37037	0.6812	27.383
11	4.574074	0.5356	1.148148	0.5287	33.452
12	4.537037	0.6926	1.12963	0.3390	32.470
13	3.296296	1.1595	1.092593	0.4459	13.035
14	4.62963	0.4874	1.148148	0.5287	35.577
15	3.518519	1.3422	1.037037	0.2722	13.315

16	3.537037	1.3834	1.481481	1.0594	8.669
17	4.574074	0.6019	1.296296	0.7172	25.725
18	4.62963	0.4874	1.333333	0.7268	27.678
19	4.648148	0.4820	1.037037	0.2722	47.937
20	4.555556	0.6344	1.259259	0.6200	27.307
21	4.62963	0.4874	1.296296	0.7172	28.248
22	4.537037	0.6926	1.222222	0.5719	27.119
23	4.537037	0.6926	1.055556	0.4082	31.821
24	3.388889	1.3656	2.055556	1.3656	5.073
25	4.574074	0.6019	1.481481	0.9264	20.571

Relation of statement score to total score:

Empirical validity measures the extent to which the scale results agree with the external facts related to the behavior that the scale measures. It is considered one of the most used types of honesty in psychological measures when there is an honest criterion that measures the same property or indicates it (Rabi`, 1994: 101). The researcher calculated the Pearson correlation coefficient between the score of each statement and the total score on the reciprocal Interpersonal Trust scale, and then calculated the T value of the correlation coefficient for each The statements. It was found that all the statements are statistically significant at the level (0.05) because the T value calculated for the correlation coefficient is greater than the tabular value (1.96) with a degree of freedom (198), see Table (4).

Table (4)

Statement score correlation coefficients for overall score for Interpersonal Trust reciprocal statements

No	R	T- value
1	0.933	36.53
2	0.685	13.23
3	0.922	33.46
4	0.7	13.81
5	0.609	10.80
6	0.94	38.88
7	0.947	41.32
8	0.9	29.13
9	0.95	42.98
10	0.913	31.57
11	0.94	38.66
12	0.945	40.56
13	0.704	13.96
14	0.943	39.80
15	0.721	14.64
16	0.58	10.01
17	0.925	34.30
18	0.919	32.72
19	0.955	45.40
20	0.916	32.21
21	0.926	34.55
22	0.931	35.78
23	0.939	38.28
24	0.421	6.53
25	0.887	27.06

Reliability of scale:

The reliability of the Interpersonal Trust Mutual Scale was verified in two ways:

1- Method of retesting:

The reciprocal Interpersonal Trust scale was applied twice with an interval of (21) days between the two applications, on the individuals of the Reliability sample of (50) educational advisors, chosen randomly from the sample of statistical analysis, and the Pearson correlation coefficient was used to calculate the Reliability of the

test, reaching (0.82). As the scale is good, its reliability coefficient ranged between (0.60-0.85) (Gronlund, 1981, p.125).

2- Internal consistency using the equation of Fakrobenach:

The reliability of the interpersonal trust scale was calculated using the Fakrobenach equation, and the responses of the Reliability sample were used to re-test in the reliability calculation and it reached (0.85), which is a good reliability coefficient and the scale is suitable for measuring the interpersonal trust.

Second: Positive Mood Scale:

Description of Positive Mood in original form:

Watson and others (Watson et al., 1988) prepared a Positive Mood scale, consisting of (10) words indicating Positive Mood, and the answer was according to a five-point scale (from very much = 5, to, never = 1), and the lowest score An individual obtains (10) scores, the highest is (50), and the count of (30) is the cut-off threshold and above, which is a function of Positive Mood (Watson et al., 1988, p.1068).

Positive Mood scale procedures for current research:

Validity of the scale: The validity of the scale is an indicator of the extent to which the scale measures what was developed for the purpose of measuring it (Pallant, 2010, p. 156). The researcher verified the indicators of validity (translation and apparent validity and construct validity) of the scale as follows:

1- Authenticity of translation: The researcher translated the Watson and others scale of positive mood into Arabic, and the procedures included the following:

The translated version was presented to a group of experts in psychological sciences and English bilingual experts to express their opinions about the translation and to make appropriate adjustments to the translated vocabulary to fit the research sample, the educational counselors. The agreement in translating the vocabulary in both cases reached (95%).

2- The apparent validity: The apparent validity of the scale was verified as in the procedures of the first tool in the research and the appropriateness of the vocabulary of Positive Mood scale and its instructions. It was presented in a questionnaire on (10) arbitrators from specialists in psychological sciences.

Table (5)

The value of (Chi-square) to denote differences on the vocabulary of the positive mood scale

Items of the scale	Items number	Jury numbers		Chi-square		Sig level
Enthusiastic, assertive, attentive, careful, in case you are excited	5	9	1	6.40	3.84	sig
Energetic, passionate, caring, proud, in an important situation	5	10	0	10.00	3.84	sig

The approval of (9) arbitrators or more was adopted as a criterion for the appropriateness of the terms for the current research sample, because the difference between the number of approvers and disagreements among the arbitrators is statistically significant at the level of (0.05), and the value of (Ka2) calculated (6.40) is greater than the value of (Ka2) tabular (3.84) with a degree of freedom (1) See Table (5), and no statement was excluded from the scale.

- Statistical analysis of the scale statements:

The discriminatory power of the statements: The researcher adopted the same procedures that it applied with the interpersonal trust scale, and to achieve the discrimination of the statements, the Positive Mood scale was applied to the statistical analysis sample drawn from the research community consisting of (200) educational advisors, and (27%) of the sample members were approved in determining the two higher groups. After applying the scale to the sample, the answers were arranged in descending order from the highest total score to the lowest overall score, then a percentage (27%) was determined for the two extremist groups of educational counselors, so the number of educational counselors became (54) educational counselors in each group. And the use of the t-test for two independent samples to find out the significance of the differences between the two extreme groups in the scores of each statement of the interpersonal trust scale, so all the items of the scale appeared distinct at the level (0.05) because the calculated T value is greater than the tabular T-value (1.96) with a degree of freedom (106)), See Table (6).

Table (6)

The strength of distinguishing the positive mood scale items

No	Upper Group	Lower group	T - value
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	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
1	3.666667	0.672927	1.333333	0.513956	20.250
2	3.888889	0.60397	1.296296	0.460911	25.076
3	3.833333	0.636915	1.407407	0.566969	20.906
4	3.703704	0.662461	1.185185	0.392095	24.042
5	3.703704	0.662461	1.37037	0.524721	20.289
6	3.907407	0.622488	1.296296	0.460911	24.773
7	3.722222	0.596109	1.314815	0.468803	23.327
8	3.648148	0.587846	1.222222	0.419643	24.682
9	3.796296	0.683488	1.314815	0.468803	22.001
10	3.833333	0.770934	1.388889	0.529031	19.212

calculated between the score of each of the items and the overall score on the Positive Mood scale, and the T value of the Singular Correlation Coefficient was extracted, so it was found that all the scale items are statistically significant at the level of (0.05) because the T value of the correlation coefficient is greater than the tabular value (1.96) with a degree of freedom (198), see Table (7).

Table (7)

The coefficient of correlation of the statement with the total score of the scale

No	Items	R	T-value
1	strong	0.86	23.71
2	proud	0.886	26.89
3	interested	0.865	24.26
4	In an important case	0.89	27.47
5	In an excited case	0.873	25.19
6	Enthusiastic	0.889	27.32
7	firm	0.871	24.95
8	attentive	0.885	26.75
9	careful	0.89	27.47
10	active	0.871	24.95

Reliability of scale:

- Internal consistency using the Fachrobnach equation: To verify the internal consistency of the Positive Mood scale, the Cronbach Alfa equation was used by adopting the answers of a sample drawn from the statistical analysis sample and amounted to (50) educational guides, and the coherence coefficient was (0.89), which is an indicator of good reliability of internal consistency. Positive Mood.

Application of the two research tools: To achieve the objectives of the current research, they were applied to the basic research sample of (150) educational advisors, see Table (2).

Statistical means: To achieve the objectives of the current research, the following statistical methods were used:

The T-test for two independent samples, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, and the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient, the T-test for one sample.

Displaying and interpreting search results:

1- The first goal:

The first objective measures the mutual interpersonal trust of educational counselors. To achieve this, the T-test was used for one sample, and the results showed that the average interpersonal trust score for the research sample is equal to (91.4067) degrees, and with a standard deviation of (16.83002) degrees. The difference was in statistical significance at the level of (0.05), as the calculated T value reached (11.939), which is greater than the tabular T value (1.96) with a degree of freedom (149), and Table (8) illustrates that.

Table (8)

One sample t-test result for sample scores on the Interpersonal Trust Scale

Sample	Hypothetical mean	Mean	S.D	Degree of freedom	T- value		sig
					calculated	tabular	
150	75	91.4067	16.83002	149	11.939	1.96	0.05

The result showed a statistically significant difference between the average of the sample and the theoretical mean of the scale, which shows that educational counselors in general have a level of mutual interpersonal trust, as the behavior, interaction and communication between the educational counselor and the mentor is not just a matter of exchanging information, but rather the nature of the relationship is determined and controlled. Consequently, it leads to the consolidation of mutual trust between them, and this is what was revealed by the study (Dillard et al. 1996). The trust that is built in relationships is in the long term, and the need for actions that guide individuals in a stable normative framework (Dillard et al. 1996, p. 703).

2- The second objective: The second objective was devoted to measuring Positive Mood among educational counselors. To achieve this, the T-test was used for one sample T-test, and the results showed that the average of Positive Mood scores for the research sample equals (36.4800) degrees and a standard deviation of (11.51755) degrees, the significance of the difference between the sample mean and the theoretical mean of the scale of (30). It became clear that the difference was statistically significant at the level (0.05), as the calculated T value reached (6.891), which is greater than the tabular T value (1.96) with a degree of freedom (149), see table (9).

Table (9)
The result of the T-test for one sample for the sample scores on a positive mood scale

Sample	Hypothetical mean	Mean	S.D	Degree of freedom	T- value		sig
					calculated	tabular	
150	30	36.4800	11.51755	149	6.891	1.96	0.05

This result indicates that the educational counselors have in general Positive Mood, and this may be due to their development of coping strategies to deal with the pressures that arise as a result of their social interaction with the counselors' problems, and this is what was indicated by (Biggest, 2015). As the educational counselor becomes able to be more able to focus on the present moment with the general goal and how to manage the building of Positive Mood and maintain his emotional balance.

3- The third objective: To identify the relationship between the mutual Interpersonal Trust and Positive Mood among educational counselors.

To achieve this goal, the researcher calculated the correlation coefficient between the educational counselors' scores in the mutual Positive Mood and the Interpersonal Trust, and the correlation coefficient between them was (0.145). To verify the significance of this relationship, the T-test for the significance of the correlation coefficient was used, as shown in Table (10). It was evident from the results that there was no statistically significant relationship between Interpersonal Trust and Positive Mood.

Table (10)
Coefficient of correlation between Interpersonal Trust Mutual and Positive Mood for educational counselors

Variables	R	T- value	
		calculated	tabular
Interpersonal Trust and Positive Mood	0.145	1.78	1.96

Conclusions:

In light of the research results, the researcher concludes the following:

Educational counselors enjoy a mutual interpersonal trust.

- Educational counselors enjoy Positive Mood.

- There is no significant correlational relationship between Positive Mood and the mutual Interpersonal Trust for educational counselors.

Recommendations:

In light of the results that have been reached, the researcher recommends the following:

- Promote and enhance Positive Mood among educational counselors through regular seminars and training programs to keep Positive Mood relaxed, stimulated and sustained in them.
- Holding training workshops and seminars to increase social interaction to enhance the mutual interpersonal trust.

The proposals:

- Conducting a similar study on the interpersonal trust and its relationship to other variables such as social integration
- Conducting a similar study on educational counselors and female counselors according to the gender variable, and comparing its results with the current research.
- Conducting a similar study on Positive Mood and its relationship to other variables such as self-transcendence and others.

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